

**A STUDY OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTERNET USAGE AND STUDY
HABITS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

Dr. Arundhati Chavan

Deputy Director, Distance Education, SNTD Women's University, Mumbai-49

Sadhana Pote-Palsamkar

Research scholar, Department of Education, SNTD Women's University, Mumbai-20

Abstract:

Internet have entered and revitalized fields including education. The effect of internet on students is ever increasing day by day and it is also affecting their academics. The present paper is based on the information provided by the secondary school students of Thane district. The survey method was used to collect the data. The rating scale was designed, keeping in view the objectives of this study. The study reveals that there is significant relationship between internet usage and study habits of secondary school students.

Keywords: *Internet Usage, Study Habits, Secondary School Students.*

Introduction:

Internet is most effective and fastest growing technology that society has ever seen. Internet have occupied significant place in our life. Internet is used by millions of people everyday for the purpose communication, social networking, information, entertainment, shopping and education. Majority of users belong to the age-group of 18-25yrs.

Internet usage is common among students and they spend hours on social networking sites, WWW surfing, watching entertainment programs. The use of internet can be beneficial or harmful for the students; it all depends on the frequency, purpose, time for which it is being used. The researches show that internet use that interferes with social or academic functioning. Internet use has major impact on the personal, social, academic life of students. Though students use internet for learning, surfing academic information, projects/ researches;

but the most famous online activities of students is social networking. So one can understand that internet is both boon and bane for students. (Sancheti, 2012)

Need of the study:

The internet has become an evitable part of life for many youngster and they are spending significant amount of their time on the internet. Adolescent's now-a-days using internet mainly for socialization, such as chat-rooms and messengers, entertainment such as downloading music and amusement such as online games.

Internet has become a gateway mainly for adolescents to spend a substantial amount of time each day. Although the internet seems to be a "New Found Land" for the adolescents, research has suggested that people who are engaged in internet more were likely to experience a reduce of their social network, increase of loneliness, depression, daily stress and importantly it's affecting their school studies. It is certainly true that one can have more control, less threatened and feel less inhibited in online communication; however, there are risks in doing online communication as people can alter their own identity on the net. This may post danger to adolescents, as they may fall into the scams and many be used by others. Moreover, by spending excessive time on the internet, it also reduces their chances of socializing with others in real life.

Operational definitions:

Internet usage: Internet usage can be defined as "use of internet for socialization, obtaining information, entertainment, communication, emailing."

Study habits: Study habits can be defined as "Students different abilities, interests and ways of thinking and responding to a particular thing."

Objectives of the study:

1. To study internet usage of secondary school students.
2. To study study-habits of secondary school students.
3. To study internet usage of secondary school girls students.
4. To study study - habits of secondary school girls students.
5. To study internet usage of secondary school boys students.
6. To study study-habits of secondary school boys students.
7. To study relationship between internet usage of secondary school students.
8. To study relationship between internet usage of secondary school girls students.

9. To study relationship internet usage and study habits of secondary school boys students.

Hypothesis of the study:

1. There is no significant relationship exist between internet usage and study habits of secondary school students.
2. There is no significant relationship exist between internet usage and study habits of secondary school girls students.
3. There is no significant relationship exist between internet usage and study habits of secondary school boys students.

Scope, Limitation and De-Limitation:

The study is restricted to the thane district only to English medium schools of secondary school students is taken into consideration. The study is limited to 300 students of 6 secondary schools of Thane district of Mumbai board. The study is limited to internet usage and study habits only, no other factor is taken into consideration. Urdu, Hindi, Marathi mediums schools of thane district are excluded from the study.

Methodology of the study:

The present study is based on the information provided by 300 students of 6 secondary schools of Thane district. To collect the data a structured rating scale were designed and administered. The questionnaire was designed, keeping in view the objectives of the study. The target populations for the study were girl and boy students of Urdu, Hindi, and Marathi mediums secondary schools. Multi-stage sampling technique was used for the present study. The investigators have analyzed the data with the help of descriptive statistical measures and inferential Statistical Measures.

Data analysis and Findings:

The internet usage and study habits of secondary school students of Thane district was depicted here. The data is concerned with the personal information provided by the respondents.

Table 1: Internet usage of secondary school students.

Class Interval	Frequency	Percentage
40 – 50	02	0.67
50 – 60	29	9.67

60 – 70	98	32.67
70 – 80	88	29.33
80 – 90	58	19.33
90 – 100	25	8.33
Total	300	100

Table 1 shows that 0.67% students (minimum) scored in the range of 40-50, 32.67% students (maximum) scored in the range of 60-70. 8.33% students scored in the range of 90-100.

Table 2: Study habits of secondary school students.

Class Interval	Frequency	Percentage
90- 100	01	0.3
100 – 110	-	-
110 – 120	03	1
120 - 130	08	2.67
130 – 140	31	10.33
140 – 150	60	20
150 – 160	54	18
160 – 170	68	22.67
170 - 180	42	14
180 – 190	22	7.33
190 – 200	09	3
200 – 210	02	0.67
Total	300	100

Table 2 shows that 0% students (minimum) scored in the range of 100-110, 22.67% students (maximum) scored in the range of 160-170, 0.67% students scored in the range of 200- 210.

Table 3: Internet usage of secondary school boy students.

Class Interval	Frequency	Percentage
40 – 50	01	0.58
50 – 60	09	5.29
60 – 70	62	36.47

70 – 80	56	33
80 – 90	29	17.05
90 – 100	13	7.64
Total	170	100

Table 3 shows that 0.58% students (minimum) scored in the range of 40-50, 36.47% students (maximum) scored in the range of 60-70, 7.64% students scored in the range of 90- 100.

Table 4: Study habits of secondary school boy students.

Class Interval	Frequency	Percentage
110 – 120	01	0.58
120 – 130	03	1.76
130 – 140	16	9.41
140 – 150	40	23.52
150 – 160	32	18.82
160 – 170	37	21.76
170 – 180	25	14.70
180 – 190	12	7.05
190 – 200	03	1.76
200 - 210	01	0.58
Total	170	100

Table 4 shows that 0.58% students (minimum) scored in the range of 110-120, 23.52% students (maximum) scored in the range of 140-150, 0.58% students scored in the range of 200- 210.

Table 5: Internet usage of secondary school girl students.

Class Interval	Frequency	Percentage
40 – 50	01	0.76
50 – 60	20	15.38
60 – 70	37	28.46
70 – 80	31	24
80 – 90	29	22.30
90 – 100	12	9.23

Total	130	100
--------------	------------	------------

Table 5 shows that 0.76% students (minimum) scored in the range of 40-50, 28.46% students (maximum) scored in the range of 60-70, 9.23% students scored in the range of 90- 100.

Table 6: Study habits of secondary school girl students.

Class Interval	Frequency	Percentage
90 – 100	01	0.76
100 – 110	00	-
110 – 120	02	1.53
120 – 130	05	4
130 – 140	15	11.53
140 – 150	20	15.38
150 – 160	23	17.69
160 – 170	30	23.07
170 – 180	17	13.07
180 – 190	10	7.69
190 – 200	06	4.61
200 – 210	01	0.76
Total	130	100

Table 6 shows that 0% students (minimum) scored in the range of 100-110, 23.07% students (maximum) scored in the range of 160-170, 0.76% students scored in the range of 200- 210.

Table 7: Descriptive analysis of Internet Usage of secondary school students:

Sample Size	Mean	Median	Mode	STDDEV
300	72.95858	71	69	10.18072

Table 7 shows that mean is 72. 95858 and standard deviation is 10.18072.

Table 8: Descriptive analysis of Study Habits of secondary school students:

Sample Size	Mean	Median	Mode	STDDEV
300	157.9467456	157	147	15.53538984

Table 8 shows that mean is 157.9467456 and standard deviation is 15.53538984.

Table 9: Significance of co-efficient of correlation between Internet Usage and Study Habits of secondary school students:

Sample Size	Degree of freedom (n-2)	Calculated 'r'	Tabulated 'r' at 0.05 level	LOS	Tabulated 'r' at 0.01 level
300	298	-0.459	0.113	Significant	0.148

Table 9 shows that tabulated value of 'r' according to the degree of freedom N-2 at 0.01 level is 0.148 and at 0.05 level is 0.113. The calculated value of 'r' is smaller than tabulated value of 'r', at 0.01 level. The co-efficient of correlation between internet usage and study habits is -0.459 and it shows negative relationship between internet usage and study habits.

Table 10: Significance of co-efficient of correlation between Internet Usage and Study Habits of secondary school boy students:

Sample Size	Degree of freedom (n-2)	Calculated 'r'	Tabulated 'r' at 0.05 level	LOS	Tabulated 'r' at 0.01 level
70	168	-0.35278	0.159	Significant	0.208

Table 10 shows that tabulated value of 'r' according to the degree of freedom N-2 at 0.01 level is 0.208 and at 0.05 level is 0.159. The calculated value of 'r' is smaller than tabulated value of 'r', at 0.01 level.

Table 11: Significance of co-efficient of correlation between Internet Usage and Study Habits of secondary school girl students:

Sample Size	Degree of freedom (n-2)	Calculated 'r'	Tabulated 'r' at 0.05 level	LOS	Tabulated 'r' at 0.01 level
30	128	-0.55528	0.174	Significant	0.228

Table 11 shows that tabulated value of 'r' according to the degree of freedom N-2 at 0.01 level is 0.228 and at 0.05 level is 0.174. The calculated value of 'r' is smaller than tabulated value of 'r', at 0.01 level.

Conclusions:

The data analysis of the present study revealed that internet usage has a significant negative relationship with study habits in secondary schools students. From the data analysis and findings of the present study, it was concluded that the internet usage and study habits of person are inversely proportional to each other. If the student has high internet usage then they have poor study habits. It was also concluded that there is no significant gender difference in internet usage and study habits of chosen sample.

Discussion:

The aim of this research was rather to interrupt the problematic use of online applications while continuing to use necessary ones for everyday functioning. This research is helpful for adolescents, parents, educators to overview the negative effects of internet usage and place alarm for them. Internet usage had been correlated with several factors such as study, work, job, family, mental, etc. The main reason for presenting this research was to add to this theoretical concept deep focus and plastic picture.

References:

- Best, J.W. and Kahn, J.V. (2005). Research in education (9th edition). New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
- Khan, S. (2014). A study of relationship between metacognition, achievement motivation, self regulated learning of secondary school students. Unpublished M. ed dissertation, Mumbai: SNDT Women's University.
- Sancheti, A. (2012). Impact of internet use on youth. Unpublished M. HSc. Dissertation, Mumbai: SNDT Women's University.
- Kaur, S. (2013) Academic achievement in relation to achievement motivation of high school students. International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) ISSN (Online): 2319-7064 Volume 2 Issue 12. Retrieved from <http://www.ijsr.net/archive/v2i12/MDIwMTM2NzI=.pdf> on May 23, 2013.

Copyrights @ **Dr. Arundhati Chavan & Sadhana Pote-Palsamkar** .This is an open access reviewed article distributed under the creative common attribution license which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provide the original work is cited.